

ISic0091

I.Sicily inscription 0091

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [imp(eratori)Caes(ari)L(ucio)Septi]miø
2. [SeveroPertin]açi Aug(usto)
3. [ArabicoAdiabe]nico pon [tif(ici)max(imo)] trib(unicia) · potest(ate) · V ·
imp(eratori)
5. [VIIIc]o(n)s(uli) II [p(atri)p(atriciae)imp(eratoris)] Caesaris
6. [di]vi · M(arci) · An[t]onini · Germ(anici)
7. [Sarm(atici)fi]l(io) divi Commodi
8. [fratri] divi Antonini Pii
9. [nepotid]i[v]i Hadriani pro
10. [pr]onepoti divi Traiani
11. [P]arthici abnepoti divi
12. Nervae adnepoti in
13. dulgentissimo et cle
14. mentissimo principi
15. Maesia Fabia Titiana
16. c(larissima) · f(emina) · et
17. Maesius · Fabius · Titia
18. nus · c(larissimus) · p(uer)

19.

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285281

EDR 127502

EDCS 22100044

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum.* Berlin. At 10.7343 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650795>)

Bivona, L. 1994. *Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica.* Palermo / Rome. At 7

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0091. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4334095>